

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF OIL/OIL EMULSION FORMED BY DIFFERENT RATIOS OF CYCLOHEXANE AND ETHYLENE GLYCOL STABILISED BY THE SURFACTANTS 0.5% AT $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Cyclohexane/ ethylene glycol ratio	Surface tension dyne cm^{-1}	Viscosity m poise	Conductance $\times 10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
<i>Ambucon Pdr.</i>			
1 : 1	37.77	139.75	41.5
1 : 2	36.98	146.21	40.0
1 : 3	36.23	158.33	38.5
1 : 4	35.78	174.09	37.0
1 : 5	35.076	184.13	35.0
1 : 6	34.71	193.77	33.5
1 : 7	34.04	205.70	31.5
1 : 8	33.388	211.75	30.0
1 : 9	32.043	221.12	28.0
<i>Super-N-Dedanol</i>			
1 : 1	48.32	159.48	6.3
1 : 2	47.32	165.26	5.8
1 : 3	46.45	171.31	5.3
1 : 4	45.85	177.34	4.7
1 : 5	44.74	183.24	4.2
1 : 6	44.17	189.46	3.6
1 : 7	43.13	195.12	3.1
1 : 8	42.14	201.28	2.5
1 : 9	41.64	207.37	2.0
<i>Cetyl alcohol</i>			
1 : 1	37.77	139.75	41.5
1 : 2	36.98	146.21	40.0
1 : 3	36.23	158.33	38.5
1 : 4	35.78	174.09	37.0
1 : 5	35.076	184.13	35.0
1 : 6	34.71	193.77	33.5
1 : 7	34.04	205.70	31.5
1 : 8	33.388	211.75	30.0
1 : 9	33.043	221.12	28.0

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF WATER ON PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CYCLOHEXANE/ETHYLENE GLYCOL EMULSION (1 : 1) STABILISED BY CETYL ALCOHOL (0.5%) AT $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Water ml	Surface tension dyne cm^{-1}	Viscosity m poise	Conductance $\times 10^{-4} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
10	37.65	64.81	3.5
20	39.08	48.80	3.8
30	41.10	45.96	4.0
40	42.79	40.60	4.3
50	44.04	36.16	4.5
60	46.59	31.91	4.6
70	48.72	27.51	4.8
80	51.05	21.66	5.1
90	54.37	16.98	5.4
100	57.20	11.93	5.8

cyclohexane/ethylene glycol ratios in the case of cetyl alcohol as surfactant. This indicates the importance of OH group in the emulsifications.

Table 2 shows that with cetyl alcohol when the percentage of water increases, adverse effect is observed, viz. the viscosity decreases while surface tension increases. Earlier results have shown that decreased stability results from lower viscosity and higher surface tension. Thus, diminished stability can be related to the changes in the ability of hy-

drogen bond formation due to the presence of water in conformity of the first two observations.

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Effect of Temperature on the Conductance of Oil/Oil Emulsions Stabilised by Cationic and Nonionic Surfactants

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THE conductance of the oil/water emulsions have been measured by various workers to study the effect of concentration¹, emulsification time and temperature, phase-volume ratio, temperature², ageing effect³ etc. A survey of literature reveals that oil/oil emulsions have been investigated to a very limited extent⁴. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to prepare kerosene oil/ethylene glycol and turpentine oil/ethylene glycol emulsions and study the effect of temperature on the conductance.

Experimental

Double-distilled kerosene oil (sp. gr. 0.7937), turpentine oil (sp. gr. 0.8745) and ethylene glycol (B.D.H.), cetyl alcohol and Acifix (CSAN) (HICO, India) were used. The oil/oil emulsions were prepared by agent-in-oil method. The studies were conducted at 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60° and the surfactant concentration at 0.5%, keeping the oil/oil ratio constant at 1 : 3. The conductance was measured using a conductivity bridge. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF EMULSIFICATION TEMPERATURE ON CONDUCTANCE OF OIL/OIL EMULSIONS

Oil/oil ratio = 1 : 8, Cetyl alcohol/Acifix = 0.5%

Emulsi- fication temp. °C	Conductance $\times 10^3 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$			
	Kerosene oil/ Ethylene glycol		Turpentine oil/ Ethylene glycol	
	Cetyl alcohol	Acifix	Cetyl alcohol	Acifix
20	5.05	7.10	10.20	12.21
30	5.55	7.65	10.80	12.81
40	5.90	7.95	11.10	13.12
50	6.21	8.27	11.70	13.73
60	6.85	8.90	12.30	14.73

Results and Discussion

The emulsions kerosene oil/ethylene glycol and turpentine oil/ethylene glycol stabilised by cetyl alcohol and Acifix start demulsification as the temperature is increased resulting in continuous increase in conductivity value (Table 1). The effects of demulsification and conductance increase with the rise of temperature are also due to the decrease in the aggregation of particles⁵. Thus it is concluded that as the temperature is increased the demulsification starts and the emulsions become dilute and less stable.

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Synthesis of 2-Arylindoles via Aza-ring Closure of Sulphonium Salts

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MANY routes have been devised to synthesise 2-arylindoles, but the methods are not versatile because the reactions involve drastic reaction conditions. Hirroze *et al.*¹ reported the reaction of *N*-phenacylpyridinium bromide with anilines to furnish 2-phenylindoles. Junjappa² extended this reaction using phenacyldimethylsulphonium bromide. Bansal *et al.*^{3,4} reported the synthesis of indole derivatives by the interaction of phenacylpyridinium and arsonium bromides. These workers

suggested that the reaction occurred by the nucleophilic attack of amino group of aniline on the carbonyl group of pyridinium and arsonium salt to form an intermediate which underwent ylide formation; the latter subsequently cyclised to indole. These observations were in contrast to the suggestion of Junjappa² who reported the course of reaction via an initial ylide intermediate. These contradictory observations led us to reinvestigate the course of reaction of sulphonium ylides and their salts with substituted anilines.

Experimental

The substituted-phenacyl bromides were prepared⁵ by reacting substituted-acetophenones with Br_2 in ether-dioxan solution. All the sulphonium salts (1a-c) were prepared according to the reported procedure⁶⁻⁸.

Reaction of sulphonium salts (1a-c) with aromatic amines:

2-Arylindoles (3a-1): A mixture of sulphonium salt (1a-c) (10 mmol) and aromatic amine (2; 30 mmol) was refluxed in *N,N*-dimethylaniline (50 ml) for 4–8 h. The mixture was then cooled, neutralised with 20% HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) and the solvent evaporated to give a solid which was recrystallised from appropriate solvents or solvent mixtures shown in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The method consists of the reaction of *p*-substituted-phenacyldimethylsulphonium bromides (1a-c) with substituted-anilines (2a-1) in dimethylaniline at reflux temperature to give 2-substituted-phenylindoles (3a-1) in 40–70% yields. The reaction can also be carried out using triethylamine, but with lower yield.

A plausible mechanism of the reaction of sulphonium salts (1a-c) with various anilines (2a-1) is similar to that of analogous pyridinium⁹ and arsonium⁴ salts. Another possible route for the formation of indole derivatives (4a-1) could be via initial conversion of the sulphonium bromide (1a-c) to the corresponding ylide. This ylide further reacts with anilines to yield indole derivatives as reported by Junjappa². This possibility was however discarded in view of the fact that the enhanced stability of ylides resulting from delocalisation of negative charge on to carbonyl oxygen was expected to diminish its reactivity towards aniline. This was supported by the observations that the indole derivatives (3a-1) could be obtained by the ylides only when aniline hydrobromide was used. The ylide being a stronger base than aniline, would also react with anilinium bromide to form aniline and the corresponding sulphonium salt (1a-c), the latter was subsequently attacked on